

Composition-Dependent Struggle Between Iodine and Tin Chemistry at the Surface of Mixed Tin/Lead Perovskites

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Abstract

Tin alloying is a promising strategy to reduce lead content in metal halide perovskites solar cells and to modulate the perovskite band gap. Mixed tin–lead perovskites have shown photovoltaic efficiencies approaching those of lead perovskites and improved long-term stability compared to that of pure tin perovskites. We here demonstrate that the recent success of mixed perovskites lies in a composition-dependent struggle between tin and iodine chemistry at the material's surface. Tin oxidation, which plagues tin perovskite-based devices with low efficiency and thermodynamic instability, is hindered in mixed $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$ by the competition with oxidation of iodine-related defects, the latter being generally favored by both thermodynamics and kinetics. Tin oxidation can be promoted, however, under Sn-poor conditions. When Sn is alloyed to Pb in low concentrations, it acts as a dopant and Sn(IV) is promptly formed on the perovskite surface.

Metal halide perovskites are the most promising candidates for use in the future photovoltaics industry by virtue of their outstanding optoelectronic properties. [\(1–7\)](#) The best-performing devices, with photoconversion efficiencies above 25%, are based on lead halide perovskites (LHPs), [\(8\)](#) which have indeed received most of the attention of the scientific community in the past 10 years. Characterization of the remarkable properties of LHPs, such as the slow bimolecular recombination coefficients [\(9–15\)](#) and good defect tolerance, [\(16–23\)](#) has provided valuable advancements from a basic science perspective. However, lead being a toxic element, [\(24,25\)](#) the mass-market introduction of devices containing this element in sizable concentrations poses serious problems, also in view of the ongoing efforts to reduce the impact of anthropization. For this reason, procedures to recycle lead in non-aqueous environments have been recently explored, [\(26\)](#) and strategies to reduce the dimensionality and depth of the perovskite thin films have been deployed. [\(27,28\)](#) In this context, replacement or reduction of the lead content in the perovskite by substitution with less toxic elements *while* retaining the optoelectronic properties observed for LHPs represents a compelling challenge in this research field. [\(29\)](#)

Currently tin is the only viable alternative to lead with significant efficiency [\(30,31\)](#) among those investigated, e.g., germanium [\(32\)](#) and combinations of group I/III metals such as Bi and Ag. [\(33–35\)](#) While tin halide perovskites (THPs) possess interesting optoelectronic properties, such as low exciton binding energies and lower band gaps compared to LHPs, [\(36–38\)](#) photoconversion efficiencies only up to ~13%

have been recorded. (39–41) Such a performance gap relative to LHPs originates from the self-p-doping characteristics of THPs, which, coupled to the facile oxidation of Sn(II) to Sn(IV), ultimately lead to enhanced non-radiative recombination and thermodynamic instability of the material. (31,42–46) In fact, the heavy THPs' p-doping favors the nucleation of surface Sn(IV) centers which, in turn, act as electron traps that promote recombination and lattice degradation toward secondary phases, e.g., MA_2SnI_6 and SnI_4 for MASnI_3 (MA = methylammonium). (46)

Recently, promising results have been obtained for mixed tin/lead perovskites which have shown solar-to-electrical power conversion efficiencies up to 20%. (47–49) These encouraging developments indicate that such systems could become competitive with LHPs. The key factors favoring the use of mixed perovskites are their tunable band gap (44,50) and their peculiar defect chemistry. (45) Density functional theory (DFT) calculations demonstrated that the defect activity in lead (tin) iodide perovskites is dominated by iodine (tin) chemistry, which is responsible of the formation of deep hole (electron) traps. (45) In contrast, 50:50 tin/lead perovskites show an intermediate behavior which could possibly make them potentially free of deep traps. (45) Furthermore, the reduced p-doping of $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$, with the Fermi level 0.4 eV above the valence band (VB), compared to MASnI_3 (45) (Fermi level at the VB) may partially suppress tin oxidation. (46)

One may actually note that LHPs are already defect-tolerant. (17–23) This is indeed true for the bulk material, due to the combined effects of energy barriers associated with hole trapping and the polaronic nature of the charge carriers, (14) which reduces the probability of defect-mediated recombination. (51) However, charge recombination at the surface of LHPs (52–54) can play a major role in undermining the performance of the device and initiating the degradation of the material. (55,56) It is, therefore, quintessential to appropriately tailor the surface properties of LHPs to curtail these noxious phenomena. (57) In this regard, passivation strategies have been successfully deployed to deactivate surface defect states, with a beneficial impact on the photoconversion efficiency. (58–62) In contrast, the role of defects at the surface of mixed tin/lead perovskites has not received comparable attention. Experiments have shown that low contents of Sn in the perovskite (0.5–20%) translate into poor optoelectronic properties, with a dramatic increase in non-radiative recombination. (63) At variance with this, surface treatments, such as vacuum-assisted growth and annealing, (64,65) addition of passivating layers, (66) and inclusion of excess Sn powder in the precursor solution, (48) were found to be beneficial in reducing the concentration of surface traps, which are associated with surface-activated corrosion. (67) A comprehensive understanding on the electronic properties and the defect chemistry of mixed tin/lead perovskites is thus highly desirable to further boost the optoelectronic quality of these lead-alleviated materials.

In this Letter, we unveil a composition-dependent competition between tin and iodine defect activities at the surface of mixed tin/lead perovskites. By means of advanced *ab initio* calculations, we show that formation of surface Sn(IV), at the root of the poor efficiency and of the instability of tin halide perovskites, is hindered in $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$ by the struggle between tin and iodine chemistry, with beneficial effects on the material's optoelectronic properties and, in turn, on the long-term stability. In stark contrast, alloys with low tin content are dramatically affected by tin oxidation, thus explaining the observed optoelectronic properties measured in recent experiments.

We perform hybrid DFT calculations (cf. [Supporting Information](#)) on MI_2 -terminated (M = Sn/Pb) (001) surfaces of $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$, as such unpassivated systems serve as extreme examples of surface chemistry in mixed tin/lead compounds. We do not include MAI-covered surfaces, as they have shown low reactivity

and bulk-like electronic properties in both LHPs and THPs. (46,55) We first consider two bulk models: (i) one in which $\text{Pb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_2$ planes occur along the c direction and (ii) one in which layers of PbI_2 and SnI_2 are alternated along the c direction (bulk 1 and bulk 2, respectively, in Figure 1; cf. Supporting Information for details). Bulk 2 is calculated to be 0.08 eV more stable than bulk 1, in line with previous estimates. (68) From bulk 1, we construct a stoichiometric apolar (001)- $\text{Pb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_2$ terminated slab (surface 1). From bulk 2, we construct symmetric SnI_2 -terminated (surface 2) and PbI_2 -terminated slabs (surface 3), which represent two limit conditions of full Pb and Sn coverage, respectively (cf. Figure 1). These models are apolar, but their Pb:Sn ratio is either 0.6:0.4 or 0.4:0.6. Therefore, we here focus on the stoichiometric surface 1, while surfaces 2 and 3 are discussed in the Supporting Information.

Figure 1

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the bulk models of $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$ and the related (001) surfaces. Pb atoms are given in brown, Sn in yellow, I in pink, C in cyan, N in blue, and H in white. The tetragonal axis lies horizontally for bulk models, while a view with the z axis lying vertically represents the slabs.

As a first step, we investigate the self-trapping process of holes on the pristine surface. Our calculations show that charge localization can occur in three different ways upon injection of a single hole into the system (cf. Figure 2):

- (i) Formation a surface hole polaron with binding energy of 0.19 eV, a value slightly larger than that estimated for the bulk (cf. Supporting Information) and in line with previous results on the PbI_2 -terminated MAPbI_3 surface. (55)
- (ii) Formation of a so-called a V-center, (69) a typical defect occurring in metal halides. (70–72) This is originated by the displacement of a neutralized iodine from its lattice site to form a bridging I_2^- dimer with a bond length of 3.28 Å (i.e., a neutral interstitial iodine I_i^0 , cf. Figure 2) and a positively charged iodine vacancy V_i^+ :

(1)

- (iii) Hole trapping on a distorted surface SnI_5^- , upon contraction of Sn–I bonds by ~ 0.1 up to 0.3 Å with respect to the neutral system (cf. [Figure 2](#)). This structure represents a precursor to the formation of surface Sn(IV) previously encountered in tin perovskites. [\(46\)](#)

Figure 2

Figure 2. Schematic representation of hole-trapping species on the pristine (001) surface 1 model of $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$. Pb atoms are given in brown, Sn in yellow, I in pink, C in cyan, N in blue, and H in white; an isodensity representation of the hole is given in purple. The z axis lies vertically. For the precursor surface trap and Sn(IV), we provide the Sn–I bond lengths of the involved Sn atom to be compared to those calculated for a surface Sn on the neutral and positively charged pristine slabs. For the iodide dimer and trimer, we provide the respective bond lengths. All values are given in Å.

The surface hole polaron is promptly formed upon structural relaxation of the slab with an extra hole. Furthermore, it is found to be slightly more stable than the V-center (precursor trap state) by 0.19 (0.10) eV. Linear transit calculations (cf. [Supporting Information](#)) [\(73\)](#) indicate that the surface polaron \rightarrow V-center (precursor trap state) charge localization process entails an energy barrier of 0.26 (0.24) eV (cf. [Figure 3a](#)).

Figure 3

Figure 3. Energy diagrams of species trapping (a) one hole and (b) two holes on the pristine (001) surface 1 model of $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$ and on the surface bearing a Sn vacancy and an interstitial I. In each diagram, energies are referred to that of the most stable species, which is highlighted with a thicker horizontal line.

We then consider the trapping of a second hole. For the system bearing the V-center, we observe the spontaneous formation of an interstitial/vacancy I_i^+/V_1^+ iodine Frenkel defect (IFD) (74) (cf. Figure 2) via the following reaction:

in which the formation of a positively charged interstitial iodine (I_i^+), formally an I_3^- moiety, is envisaged. Direct IFD formation by capture of two holes from the pristine perovskite via

is energetically favorable by 0.81 eV. However, a substantial energy barrier (0.74 eV, cf. Figure 3b) is associated with reaction (3). Therefore, the occurrence of the IFD is likely subdued compared to that of the V-center. Similarly, injection of a second hole onto the precursor trap state leads to Sn(IV) with further contraction of the Sn–I bonds. Direct Sn(IV) formation via

while being exothermic by 0.89 eV, is also hindered by a significant energy barrier (cf. [Figure 3b](#)).

So far, our analysis suggests a competition between iodine and tin defects for trapping photogenerated holes, with almost isoenergetic pathways. The precursor step to IFD formation is the capture of a hole on the V-center, which is moderately unfavorable by both kinetics and thermodynamics (cf. [Figure 3](#)). Tin oxidation is also disadvantaged for similar reasons, as the surface trap, which is a precursor to Sn(IV), is likewise metastable and its occurrence implies overcoming an energy barrier. Furthermore, the simultaneous trapping of two holes for both IFD and Sn(IV) is strongly hindered by kinetics. These results, combined with the mild p-doped electronic nature of $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$, characterized by a Fermi level predicted at 0.4 eV above the VB, [\(45\)](#) indicate that both IFDs and Sn(IV) are unlikely to be formed, even on a highly reactive unpassivated surface, thus drastically reducing the concentration of recombination centers at the surface. This is at variance with MASnI_3 , where the heavy p-doping may promote the spontaneous oxidation of tin and degradation of the material. [\(45,46\)](#)

The delicate equilibrium between iodine and tin chemistry at the surface of mixed tin/lead perovskites can be perturbed when considering common point defects in the material, such as I interstitials and Sn vacancies. In MAPbI_3 , both I and Pb defects are notably related to iodine chemistry: in fact, Pb vacancies stabilize the formation of neutral and positively charged interstitial iodine (again, related to the formation of I_2^- and I_3^- moieties, respectively) when occurring at the vacancy site. A similar phenomenon is observed upon interaction between lattice iodine and interstitial iodine. [\(55,56\)](#) However, Sn vacancies at the MASnI_3 surface were found to induce the oxidation of unsaturated Sn(II) to Sn(IV). [\(46\)](#) Therefore, both excess iodine and the presence of under-coordinated surface Sn atoms may modify the physical picture observed for the pristine surface.

We first investigate hole trapping mediated by a Sn vacancy (V_{Sn}). For a slab bearing a V_{Sn}^{2-} , we have two distinct possibilities for hole localization (cf. [Supporting Information](#) for detailed structures):

- (i) formation of a V-center at the Sn vacancy site
- (ii) hole trapping at a surface Sn(IV) precursor

Upon injection of a hole on the slab with a V_{Sn}^{2-} , we observe spontaneous localization on the Sn(IV) precursor, which is 0.20 eV more stable than the V-center. An energy barrier of 0.36 eV is estimated for the associated Sn(IV) precursor/V-center charge-transfer reaction (cf. [Figure 3a](#)). Again, the formation of an IFD is spontaneously observed upon inclusion of a second hole into the V-center, while the precursor evolves toward surface Sn(IV) (cf. [Supporting Information](#)). The IFD on the vacancy site is found to be 0.08 eV more stable than Sn(IV). As previously noted for MAPbI_3 , [\(75\)](#) the presence of a metal vacancy facilitates the interaction between neighboring lattice iodine atoms. However, in the present case, the first injected hole is preferentially trapped on the surface Sn(IV) precursor, thus favoring the reaction pathway leading to tin oxidation. Furthermore, the $\text{Sn(IV)} \rightarrow \text{I}_i^+ @ V_{\text{Sn}}^{2-}$ reaction (i.e., reduction of tin and oxidation of iodide) is curbed by a sizable energy barrier (~ 1 eV, cf. [Figure 3b](#)) due to the large structural differences among the two systems. Overall, these results denote that the Sn vacancy reinforces tin oxidation and, therefore, promotes recombination of photogenerated charge carriers.

We then consider hole-trapping mechanisms assisted by an interstitial iodine defect (cf. [Supporting Information](#) for details of the structural models). Starting from I_i^- , addition of a single hole can lead to

- (i) formation of a surface polaron (i.e., no trapping on the defect as in the pristine slab)
- (ii) formation of a metal-bridging dimer (the so-called H-center, I_i^0) between a lattice I and interstitial I upon capture of a single hole by I_i^- ([25](#))
- (iii) hole trapping at a surface Sn(IV) precursor

Introduction of a single hole on the I_i^- system results in polaron formation. However, the H-center (I_i^0) is here found to be the most stable moiety, its energy being 0.14 (0.24) eV lower than that of the surface polaron (Sn(IV) precursor). Furthermore, the surface polaron \rightarrow H-center reaction is subject to only a low energy barrier of 0.12 eV (cf. [Figure 3a](#)). In contrast, the Sn(IV) precursor is the least stable of the considered species. Again, I_3^- (corresponding to I_i^+) spontaneously appears when a second hole is added to the H-center, while Sn(IV) is achieved from the precursor trap state, the former being 0.39 eV more stable than the latter. Again, the large energy barriers associated with reactions involving two holes (cf. [Figure 3b](#)) allow us to exclude such a mechanism and also indicate that, once the charge-trapping moiety has been formed, de-trapping is highly unlikely. Overall, the present results clearly highlight how interstitial iodine defects dramatically shift the balance toward the prevalence of iodine chemistry.

The competition between iodine and tin chemistry in determining the electronic properties of the mixed perovskite is modulated by defects. In fact, for the un-defective system, a single hole is preferentially localized on the surface as a hole polaron, thus hampering charge-trapping pathways leading either to surface tri-iodide or Sn(IV). This balance can be shifted toward tin and iodide oxidation by V_{Sn} and I_i , respectively. Such results suggest that the optoelectronic properties of the mixed perovskite can actually be tailored by choosing adequate growth conditions.

Therefore, we investigate the formation energies and charge transition levels of surface V_{Sn} and I_i at varying conditions: I-rich, I-medium, and I-poor. ([45](#)) We also consider possible electron-trapping defects such as the Sn interstitial Sn_i and the iodine vacancy V_I . The formation energies of each defect as a function of the electron chemical potential (the Fermi level of the perovskite) are illustrated in [Figure 4](#). We first comment on the difference between bulk and surface energy levels in iodine-medium conditions (middle panel of [Figure 4](#)), corresponding to stoichiometric growth conditions. For both Sn vacancy and I interstitial, we observe a remarkable difference between bulk and surface. In fact, while bulk defects feature only shallow energy levels, deep traps are observed on the surface. In particular, for V_{Sn} , we calculate the (0/+2) transition level at 0.63 eV above the VB of the material. For I_i , we find the (+1/-1) transition level at 0.75 eV above the VB. These values originate from the large stabilization of surface V_{Sn}^0 and I_i^+ , due to the occurrence of Sn(IV) and the tri-iodide, respectively. Next, we analyze how different conditions influence the defects formed on the surface. First, we note that this issue is not particularly relevant for the bulk material, since it is devoid of in-gap energy levels (cf. middle panel of [Figure 4](#)). Growth conditions are more important for the surface properties. At I-rich conditions (cf. left panel of [Figure 4](#)), V_{Sn} and I_i are found to be among the most stable defects throughout the band gap of the material. In stark contrast, hole-trapping

defects are pushed toward higher formation energies at I-poor (i.e., Sn-rich, right panel of [Figure 4](#)) conditions. Furthermore, we predict a higher concentration of Sn_i defects under such conditions. This defect, however, is actually harmless for the optoelectronic properties of the material, since it features charge transition levels above the conduction band edge (cf. [Supporting Information](#)), different from what has been observed for MASnI_3 . ([45](#)) In view of these results, we interpret the beneficial impact of the inclusion of excess Sn powder in the precursor solution, recently demonstrated by experiments, ([48](#)) as a consequence of the higher formation energies of hole-trapping surface defects under Sn-rich conditions.

Figure 4

Figure 4. Formation energies of point defects on the (001) surface 1 model of $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$ as a function of the electron chemical potential μ at different conditions. Dashed lines are shown for the respective values calculated in the bulk material. We consider the chemical potential values of Sn and I employed in ref ([45](#)): I-rich ($\mu_{\text{Sn}} = -1.39$ eV, $\mu_{\text{I}} = -0.16$ eV), I-medium ($\mu_{\text{Sn}} = -0.70$ eV, $\mu_{\text{I}} = -0.51$ eV), and I-poor ($\mu_{\text{Sn}} = 0.00$ eV, $\mu_{\text{I}} = -0.86$ eV).

Formation energies of I_i are lower than those pertinent to V_{Sn} in a wide range of chemical and electron potentials. This, in conjunction with the impervious pathway calculated for tin oxidation on the pristine surface, corroborates the prediction that surface Sn(IV) is not easily formed in $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$, even considering the extreme case of a fully unpassivated surface. This explains the higher long-term stability observed for mixed perovskites compared to pure THPs. Nevertheless, iodine chemistry can still induce hole-trapping, with a detrimental effect on the efficiency of the associated devices. ([8,47,48](#)) We thus specifically investigate an iodine-mediated degradation pathway typically observed for LHPs, ([76–78](#)) leading to release of gaseous I_2 from I_i^+ :

We calculate that [reaction \(5\)](#) is energetically unfavorable by ~ 2.3 eV (recall that I_i^+ is actually an I_3^- moiety), a value significantly higher than that previously calculated for MAPbI_3 (~ 0.9 eV). ([56](#)) While in LHPs the unfavorable energetics for I_2 release was found to be compensated by the energy gain due to the I_3^- formation, ([56](#)) this does not hold for $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$. In fact, localization of two holes on I_3^- produces a stabilization of 0.82 eV, which is not sufficient to induce the release of molecular iodine in this case. Since I_3^- formation entails an energy gain of $\sim 0.8\text{--}0.9$ eV for both MAPbI_3 ([48](#)) and $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$, the remarkable difference in the energetics of the iodine release reaction is here ascribed to the higher formation energy of

both bulk and surface V_i^+ for the mixed perovskite (cf. ref (36) and Figure 4). The present result can explain the beneficial effect of alloying in increasing the stability of perovskite-based devices. (38–40)

Surprisingly, a significant rise in non-radiative charge recombination was reported when alloying the lead perovskite with low tin content (<20%), which suggests a different physics of charge carriers under these conditions. (63) To determine the origin of such a puzzling behavior, we investigate hole-trapping on a PbI_2 -terminated slab of tetragonal $MAPbI_3$ in which we substitute a single surface Pb with a Sn atom. Addition of a first hole on this system results in the formation of the Sn(IV) precursor, which then evolves to Sn(IV) upon capture of a second hole, with structural modifications analogous to those previously described for the mixed perovskite (cf. Figure 2). A similar behavior has been reported by some of us also in Sn-doped bulk $MAPbI_3$, where hole self-trapping at substitutional tin is observed for small incorporation of the dopant in the Pb site. (68)

Hole-trapping on the pristine surface of $MAPbI_3$ is tuned by iodine chemistry, with V- and H-centers (IFDs and tri-iodide moieties) being responsible for the trapping of one (two) hole(s) on pristine and defective surfaces. (55,56) Therefore, we compare the energetics of the Sn(IV) precursor with that of an I_2^- (either V- or H-center) for the Sn-doped slab and for slabs which additionally feature a surface Pb vacancy or an I interstitial. Analogously, we investigate the energetics of surface Sn(IV) in comparison with that of IFDs and tri-iodides on pristine and defective models. The results illustrated in Figure 5a show that the Sn(IV) precursor surface trap is more stable by ~ 0.2 eV in all the considered cases, which implies a clear pathway toward tin oxidation. Concerning the trapping of two holes (cf. Figure 5b), we observe that Sn(IV) is favored over IFD formation by 0.25 eV for the pristine slab. Such an energy difference is increased (decreased) to 0.40 (0.05) eV when considering iodine defects associated with V_{Pb} (I_i). Therefore, the impact of defects on the Sn-doped $MAPbI_3$ perovskite is close to that encountered for $MAPb_{0.5}Sn_{0.5}I_3$, with tin oxidation being enhanced (disfavored) by metal vacancy (iodine interstitial). However, for the Sn-doped surface, we pinpoint that, differently from $MAPb_{0.5}Sn_{0.5}I_3$ (cf. Figure 5c,d), Sn(IV) and its precursor are found to be the most stable moieties for all the investigated systems, an instance extending the range of conditions under which tin oxidation occurs.

Figure 5

Figure 5. Energy difference (eV) between iodine-related hole-trapping species (cf. main text for definitions) and one- (a) and two-hole (b) oxidized tin moieties (cf. insets in both panels for structures and isodensity representations of holes) on pristine and defective models of the Sn-doped (001) PbI_2 -terminated surface of MAPbI_3 . Values achieved for pristine and defective models of the (001) surface of $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$ are reported in panels (c) and (d) for comparison.

To summarize, we discovered a peculiar competition between tin and iodine chemistry in determining the electronic properties at the surface of mixed tin/lead perovskites. In-depth investigation of $\text{MAPb}_{0.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}\text{I}_3$ has revealed that formation of surface Sn(IV), a harsh drawback of tin halide perovskites, competes with that of the tri-iodide, the former being favored only in the presence of Sn vacancies. The formation of these defects can, in turn, be avoided by appropriately tailoring the growth conditions, i.e., by employing Sn-rich conditions which imply higher formation energies for the hole-trapping moieties. Such a struggle hinders the oxidation of surface Sn, with beneficial effects on the optoelectronic properties and the long-term stability of the system. In contrast, strong hole-trapping associated with surface Sn(IV) on both pristine and defective surfaces of MAPbI_3 doped with a low content of Sn was found to be related to the poor electronic properties measured for perovskites incorporating only a low fraction of tin. By providing the background carrier localization pathways and associated defect chemistry, we hope this work will make it possible to further extend the uptake of lead-alleviated mixed tin/lead perovskites, bringing them to efficiencies comparable to those of pure lead perovskites.

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